

THE TASTE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC IN THE FORMATION OF HUMAN TASTE

Navoi specialized culture
school teacher

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Annotation: This article talks about the role of music in human life, its importance, content, and influence on human psyche. Music is very important in developing a person's taste. This article explains how important music culture and art are for a person psychologically and physically. Also, opinions on raising and improving the intellectual level of students through music culture lessons were presented.

Key words: music, method, art, taste, aesthetics, music culture, art , intelligence, listening to music , psychology and pedagogy, action strategy, music culture, art, intellect, listening to music, psychology and pedagogy, action strategy.

It is clear to everyone that music has existed and developed since ancient times. Music has been used by people in various situations. At the same time, many of our scientists have mentioned in their works that music cultivates human thinking and develops it. Of course, it also depends on what kind of music we listen to. Nowadays, we are witnessing an increased focus on arts and sports. Of course, the purpose of this is to raise the young generation as a healthy, artistic and aesthetic taste, loyal to their people, and a perfect person. Therefore, music is one of the leading types of education.

Several recent studies have examined the impact of music on the evaluation of food and drink, but none have relied on time-based methods. Since music and food/drink are both time-varying in nature, it would seem only appropriate to take temporality into account when studying the impact of music on the eating/drinking experience. A common method of time-based sensory evaluation of food products is time-intensity (TI), where a specific sensory attribute is measured over time. In

the present investigation, we used TI analysis to measure temporal changes in sweetness and sourness evaluations of an off-dry white wine when the music stimulus changed from a soundtrack commonly associated with sweetness to one associated with sourness instead, and vice versa. The results revealed that a change of soundtrack results in a change in taste intensity (for both sweetness and sourness) in the same direction as the change in the soundtrack. More specifically, a switch from the sweet to the sour soundtrack enhanced the intensity of sourness, whereas a switch from sour to sweet soundtrack enhanced the perceived intensity of sweetness. Potential implications for the mechanisms underlying the auditory modification of taste and opportunities for future studies are discussed.

The foundation of knowledge starts from school and pre-school educational institutions. Our children get education in these places, grow spiritually and receive education. Therefore, we should not be indifferent to their learning processes, but constantly monitor them. After all, the knowledge we are learning will determine our child's future. Music also influences students' learning and thinking. In general secondary schools, music lessons are held once a week. In these music lessons, children are engaged in several activities.

Many studies have shown that music therapists have even treated patients by playing music. When we listen to any kind of music, its character is visible in our facial expressions. For example, when we listen to music with a happy, fast rhythm, we immediately feel happy and uplifted. On the contrary, if we listen to heavy and sad music, our face will reflect our thinking. Psychotherapists have also mentioned that when listening to pleasant music, a person's internal organs synchronize. Therefore, the right music is good for the human body. In addition, sports lovers and sports enthusiasts enjoy listening to music almost every day. In this way, they feel that the processes of doing sports have been completed by getting motivation for themselves.

Music is not an innate desire for beauty, an aesthetic need. It appeared in man under the influence of work and the world around him. With the change of the

external world, the person himself also changed, in which he not only progressed physically, but also spiritually. A person's spiritual ability and, first of all, aesthetic sense gradually developed and was educated. The art of music is a powerful tool for learning about life and educating people. But the level of his service in knowledge and education depends on the power of affecting a person aesthetically and artistically. Music art is a specific type of human activity, and its task is to provide aesthetic service to society. In this sense, nothing can replace it. Music takes an active place in all spheres of social life. Thus, the aesthetic attitude to reality is expressed both in the musical works created by composers and in the artistic foundations that are brought to work, domestic life, and people's relationships. Music, like any art form, originated in ancient times, when people lived in caves, used stone tools, and covered themselves with animal skins.

His spiritual world was limited, his language was poor, and his ideas about the events around him were very unclear. But nevertheless, musical masterpieces, even if they are in the "wild" state, were created by these ancient people. Almost all forms of art were created thousands of years ago. Art appeared not only in one place, but also on several continents, in different latitudes and climatic conditions.

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